

EDUCATIONAL STATUS OF SCHEDULED CASTE STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION OF ASSAM-A CASE STUDY

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Abstract

The scheduled castes people are an integral part of Indian society. In the education system, Out of total population, scheduled caste constitutes 16.2% in our country and 6.85% in the state of Assam. Higher Education takes a central place in India. It can help to national development with the help of Human resources. The modern higher education system in India is around 157 years old from the beginning of the modern higher education. In Assam, it has more than 500 affiliated colleges and more than 20 Universities. The world's average of enrolment in higher education is 23.2 % and only 12.40% in India where, Male constitutes 11.17% Female 7.95%. The enrolment of Scheduled Castes in India is only 7% (UGC report) and 6.85% of SC people are succeeding to completed higher education in 2001 in the country. Present study attempt to focus the academic achievement of scheduled castes female in higher education of Assam. Researcher collected the data from both primary and secondary sources and he used random sampling method for the present study.

1.0.0. Introduction

The Indian caste system have been prevailing since long back; still today the values of the caste systems are held strongly. There are five different levels of the caste systems in India; they are- Brahmin, Kshatriyas, Vaishya, Sudra and Horizons (Ghuyre, 1996), they are considered as actual "castes or jatis". They never exchange their own social customs, principles and traditions with others; rather they restrict them among themselves. The expression "Schedule Caste" was first used by the

Simon Commission and embodied in the Government of India Act of 1935 in section 309. Before 1935 they were known as untouchable or exterior castes or depressed castes.

Total population of India has reached to 121 crores where as scheduled castes population are 166,635,700 (census 2011). Total population of Assam as per 2011 census is 31,169,272 of which male and female are 15,954,927 and 15,214,345 respectively. The literacy rate of Assam (census report 2011) is 73.18, where Male literacy rate is 78.81 and female is 67.27 and sex ratio for females per 1000 males are 954. There are sixteen sub-castes among scheduled caste population are found in Assam. They are – 1) Kaibartta, 2) Namasudra, 3) Jalo-Malo, 4) Hira, 5) Dhuba-Dhubi, 6) Bania, Bittal Bania 7) Bansphor, 8) Patni 9) Bhuin Mali, 10) Jalkeot, 11) Mahara, 12) Sutradhar, 13) Muchi Rishi, 14) Bhangi, 15) Dugla, and 16) Lalbegi, (Das, B 1986).

1.0.1. Higher Education in India

The modern higher education system in India has beared 158 years of glorious history that was started with the establishment of three universities in Calcutta, Bombay and Madras University in 1857. India has a large higher education system. It has more than 757 Universities, 38056 Colleges and 11,922 Stand Alone Institutions (all India survey 2014-15 report). The Literacy rate of India according to census 2011 shows male constitutes 82.14% women are 65.46% and in Assam male constitute 78.80% and women are 67.30%. The 12th five year plan brought higher education on the priority list of the government of the country on which strategies has been undertaken for its expansion with inclusiveness, quality, relevance and excellence with an aim to achieve the targeted GER (18-23) to 25% during the plan period and to 30% by 2020.

1.0.2. Higher Education in Assam

Assam, the gate way of North eastern region is a special category state. In the North eastern region of India, the growth and expansion of higher education is also

quantitative rather than qualitative particularly from the last decade. In Assam there are more than 535 colleges and more than 20 universities for higher education and Meghalaya has 05, Mizoram has 02, Nagaland has 03, Sikkim has 05, Tripura has 02, Arunachal 03 and Manipur has 02 state university, central university and private university respectively. Average 922 numbers of students are enrolled in the colleges in Assam (all India Survey 2014-15). Seats for post graduates are limited so, only limited numbers of students get access into PG studies.

Distance learning and open education is also a feature of the Indian higher education system, and is looked after by the Distance Education Council. Indira Gandhi National Open University is the largest university in the world by number of students, having approximately 3.5 million students across the globe. So, distance-education is the only answer for those who have failed to get admission to a University, or a college. Distance enrolment constitutes 11.7% of the total enrolment in higher education, of which 46% are female students.

The NKC (2005) comprehended in its scheme five aspects of knowledge paradigm such as: access to knowledge, knowledge concepts, creation of knowledge, knowledge application and delivery services. The MHRD has launched the new scheme as Rashtriya Uchchatar Shiksha Abhijan (RUSA), the national higher education mission has been drafted by MHRD to provide central funds to the state university and colleges with the objectives of helping all such institutions to go ahead for achieving the target of equity, access and excellence in higher education and thereby help the young generation in solving the basic problems of Indian society making India a super power within a short time.

2.0.0. Objectives of the study

1. To study enrolment of Scheduled Castes in higher education of Assam.
2. To study the academic achievement of Scheduled Castes in higher education of Assam.
3. To study the dropout rate of scheduled castes in higher education of Assam.

3.0.0. Delimitation

The present study covers enrolment of scheduled castes students from 2006 to 2015, academic achievement from 2008 to 2015 and drop out from 2008 to 2015. The study is also delimited as one university and its 20 numbers of affiliated colleges in Assam.

4.0.0. Significant of the Study

The scheduled castes people are also an integral part of Indian society. A good number of research study as well as research projects have been carried out in different states of India on scheduled castes; but hardly any study has been carried out in Assam so far the educational status of scheduled castes in higher education of Assam. Therefore, it is very important to study in this field for better understanding and clear picture about the enrolment of Scheduled Caste female students in the higher education in Assam. The study will help us to know Enrolment, Academic achievement, and dropout of scheduled castes in Assam. Therefore, in brief it is said that the study of “Educational status of scheduled castes in the higher education of Assam” has great significant and important in the modern age of education.

5.0.0. Methodology

Descriptive survey method is used to study the academic achievement of scheduled castes in higher education of Assam. For the present study, data are collected from both the primary sources and secondary sources.

5.0.1. Sample

Sample is taken as One University and 20 numbers of its affiliated colleges of Assam, by using purposeful sampling technique for the present study.

6.0.0. Analysis and interpretation of the Data

The present investigation was aimed at to study enrolment, academic achievement and drop out of scheduled castes in higher education of Assam. In this part an attempt has been made to describe the statistical techniques are used to analysis obtained data. In this study academic achievement and enrolment are dependent

variables.

Table No. 1. Percentage of Enrolment, Academic achievement and Dropout of Scheduled Castes in Under Graduate level

Enrolment (2006- 2015)		Academic Achievement (2006 - 2015)		Drop out (2006- 2015)	
Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male
38.60%	61.40%	39.03%	60.97%	39.45%	60.55%

The above table shows that 61.40% Male and 38.60% female enrolment, 60.97% male 39.03% female enrolment are found in the sample colleges under Dibrugarh University of Assam. Again in Dropout among scheduled caste are male 60.55%, female 39.4% respectively.

Fig.No.1. Graphical representation of Percentage of enrolment, academic achievement and Dropout of SCs in UG level

Above diagram reveals the percentage of academic achievement, and drop out of scheduled castes of total enrolment in the colleges under Dibrugarh University of Assam.

Table No.2. Total Percentage of academic achievement and Dropout of Scheduled Castes in Post Graduate level

Enrolment (2006- 2015)			Academic Achievement (2008-2015)			Drop out (2008-2015)		
Female	Male	Total	Female	Male	Total	Female	Male	Total
676	659	1335	632	615	1247	44	44	88
50.64%	49.36%	100%	50.68%	49.32%	100%	50%	50%	100%

The above table is the evidence of the total enrolment of scheduled castes in Dibrugarh University from 2001 to 2010 is 1335 where Male is 659 and Female is 676 which represents 49.36%, 50.64% respectively. The academic achievement of the University among the scheduled castes Male and Female from 2002 to 2010 are 49.32% and 50.68% respectively. Again in case of Dropout among the scheduled caste Male are 44 (50.0%) and Female are 44 (50.0%) of total drop out from 2002 to 2010 in Dibrugarh University of Assam.

Fig. No. 2. Graphical representation of percentage of enrolment, academic achievement, and drop out of SCs in PG level

The above Graphical representation is the evidence of percentage of enrolment, academic achievement and dropout of SC students in Dibrugarh University, Assam.

From the table, it is found that the enrolment among the scheduled castes female in Arts stream is 676 which are higher than the scheduled castes male 659 in the University of Assam. In science, Commerce and management it is found that the differences between male enrolments are higher than the female.

Table No. 3. Percentage of enrolment, academic achievement and Dropout of Scheduled Castes in Higher education

Enrolment		Academic Achievement		Drop out	
Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male
39.83%	60.17%	41.19%	58.81%	39.98%	60.02%

The above table represents the percentage of total Enrolment, academic achievement and dropout of SCs in Higher education of Assam.

Fig.No.3. Graphical representation of Percentage of academic achievement and Dropout of SCs in Higher education

Graphical representation shows the percentage of Enrolment, academic achievement and dropout of SCs in Higher education.

7.0.0. Findings

From the analysis of the data following finding are found.

Enrolment of Scheduled Castes in Higher Education of Assam

- From the study it is observed that Male enrolments in UG Level are 61.40% and female are 38.60% among scheduled castes student. So, male enrolments are higher than the female.
- The study shows that Urban colleges in UG Level of have higher enrolment among scheduled castes students than the semi urban and rural colleges of Assam.
- From the study it is found that total scheduled castes male and female enrolments in PG level are 50.64% and 49.36%. So, it is signified that there are slight enrolment difference between them.
- From the study it is investigated that Scheduled castes Female and male total enrolments in PG Level are 676 and 659. So, it is signified that female enrolment in PG level are higher than the male enrolment in Assam.

Academic Achievement of Scheduled Castes in Higher Education of Assam

- From the study it is found that Academic achievements in UG level among scheduled castes male are 60.97%, female are 39.03%. So, male academic achievements are higher than higher than the scheduled castes female in Assam.
- Academic achievements in PG level of scheduled castes female are 50.68% and male are 49.32. So, it is signified that female academic achievement in PG level are higher than male.
- Academic achievements in PG level of scheduled castes female in Arts stream are higher than the Science and Commerce/ Management stream of Assam.
- Academic achievements of scheduled castes female in higher education are lower than scheduled castes male which represent female 41.19% and male 58.81%.

Drop out of Scheduled Castes in Higher Education of Assam

- The study showed that Drop out percentages of scheduled castes female and

male are 39.45% and 60.55% respectively in UG level. So, male dropout rate are higher than female. In PG level, both rates are equal.

- Total Dropout rate of scheduled castes female are 39.98% and male are 60.02%. So, it is found from the study that Dropout rate of scheduled male are higher than female.

8.0.0. Conclusion

From the analysis of the data, it may be concluded that the researcher had investigated that scheduled castes female enrolment and academic achievement in higher education are lower than the male. But Dropout rate of male are higher than the female in higher education of Assam. In the sample university and its affiliated colleges Dropout rate of scheduled castes female are 39.98% and male are 60.02%. So, it is signified that scheduled castes female are highly interested to complete their higher studies in Assam. Academic achievements of SC female in Arts stream are higher than the male in Assam. From the investigation it is found that Male pass percentage are higher than female of total pass percentage of scheduled castes in the higher education of Assam. The students who are not able to pass the final examination in one sitting they appeared to the next year as private candidates among them some of the student drop out form the higher education.

9.0.0. REFERENCES:

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